
Research

Predictive Analytics: Leveraging AI for Strategic Decision-Making in Nepalese Startups

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Abstract: In the context of Nepal's burgeoning startup ecosystem, the integration of AI-powered predictive analytics has emerged as a key driver of strategic decision-making. This study investigates how startups in Nepal are utilizing predictive analytics to enhance decision accuracy, timeliness, and overall business performance. Through a survey of 267 startups, the research employs correlation and regression models to analyze the relationship between the use of predictive analytics and strategic decision-making outcomes. The study further examines how various factors, such as data quality, technological infrastructure, organizational culture, and the regulatory environment, influence the effectiveness of predictive analytics in decision-making processes. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for startup leaders, helping them to better leverage AI technologies to achieve strategic goals, and contribute to the broader understanding of the role of predictive analytics in fostering entrepreneurial success in Nepal.

Keywords: Predictive Analytics; AI, Strategic Decision-Making; Startups, Nepal

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the startup landscape in Nepal has witnessed remarkable growth, with a surge of innovative ventures aiming to address various socio-economic challenges while contributing to the nation's economic development. However, navigating the uncertainties and complexities of the market environment presents significant challenges for these nascent enterprises. To sustain growth and remain competitive, startups must make informed and strategic decisions. In this context, AI-powered predictive analytics has emerged as a transformative tool, enabling businesses to anticipate market trends, understand customer behaviors, and optimize operations with unprecedented precision. Predictive analytics refers to the use of statistical techniques, machine learning algorithms, and data mining to analyze historical and current data to make predictions about future outcomes. When integrated with AI technologies, predictive analytics becomes a powerful tool that can process vast amounts of data, identify patterns, and provide actionable insights in real time. For startups, this capability is particularly valuable as it allows for more accurate forecasting, efficient resource allocation, and the ability to respond swiftly to market changes.

Predictive analytics enables businesses to anticipate trends, behaviors, and outcomes by analyzing historical and current data (Lee, Cheang, & Moslehpour, 2022). At its core, predictive analytics encompasses a range of statistical techniques, machine learning algorithms, and data mining processes (Farayola et al., 2024). These components work together to uncover patterns and relationships within data that can be used to make informed predictions about future events. Data mining involves extracting useful information from large datasets and identifying patterns that might not be immediately apparent. Machine learning, a subset of artificial intelligence, further enhances this capability by allowing models to learn from data and improve their predictions over time (Raschka, Patterson, & Nolet, 2020). Statistical techniques, such as regression analysis, classification, and clustering, provide the mathematical foundation for analyzing data and making predictions (Daramola, Adewumi, Jacks, & Ajala, 2024a; Feng, Fan, & Chen, 2022). The potential of AI-powered predictive analytics to enhance strategic decision-making is well-documented in more developed markets. However, its application in emerging economies like Nepal remains relatively underexplored. The unique challenges faced by Nepali startups such as limited access to advanced technology, varying levels of digital literacy, and a regulatory environment that is still catching up with technological advancements necessitate a closer examination of how predictive analytics is being leveraged in this context.

This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring the impact of AI-powered predictive analytics on strategic decision-making among startups in Nepal. Specifically, it aims to investigate how these tools are used to enhance decision accuracy, timeliness, and overall business performance. Furthermore, the research will analyze how factors such as data quality and availability, technological infrastructure, organizational culture, and the regulatory environment moderate the effectiveness of predictive analytics in the decision-making process. To achieve these objectives, the study will conduct a survey of 300 startups across various sectors in Nepal. The data collected will be analyzed using correlation and regression models to determine the relationships between the use of predictive analytics and strategic decision-making outcomes. The findings are expected to provide valuable insights for startup founders and managers, offering guidance on how to effectively implement AI-driven tools to support strategic decisions and drive business growth. The significance of this research lies in its potential to inform both practitioners and policymakers. For startup leaders, understanding the role of predictive analytics in decision-making can lead to more informed strategies, better resource management, and ultimately, enhanced business performance. For policymakers, the insights gained from this study can help in crafting supportive frameworks that encourage the adoption of AI technologies in the startup ecosystem, thereby fostering innovation and economic growth in Nepal. In conclusion, as Nepali startups continue to navigate a rapidly changing business environment, the adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics presents an opportunity to gain a competitive advantage. This study will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the application of AI in business, with a specific focus on the unique challenges and opportunities within the context of Nepal. Through a detailed examination of the interplay between predictive analytics and strategic decision-making, this research aims to offer actionable insights that can support the long-term success of startups in this emerging economy.

Research Questions and objectives

- What is the impact of AI-driven predictive analytics on the performance of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups?
- How do data availability and quality affect the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and the effectiveness of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups?
- What effect does the technology infrastructure have on the performance of AI-powered predictive analytics in strategic decision-making for startups in Nepal?
- What effects do organizational culture and readiness have on the relationship between the effectiveness of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups and AI-powered predictive analytics?
- In what ways does the regulatory landscape affect the success of AI-driven predictive analytics in strategic

decision-making for companies in Nepal?

Research objectives

- To assess how well Nepali startups' strategic decision-making is affected by AI-powered predictive analytics.
- To evaluate how data availability and quality moderate the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and the effectiveness of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups.
- To examine how technology infrastructure affects the performance of AI-powered predictive analytics in strategic decision-making for Nepali startups.
- To investigate how organizational culture and preparedness affect the effectiveness of AI-driven predictive analytics in strategic decision-making for startups in Nepal.
- To ascertain how the regulatory framework affects the way in which AI-powered predictive analytics affects the performance of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups.

2. Literature review

AI-powered predictive analytics presents a great deal of promise for strategic decision-making in Nepali startups. Startups can improve their ability to forecast the market, allocate resources more efficiently, and foresee future trends by utilizing predictive models (Tuboalabo et al., 2024; Olaniyi et al., 2023). The amalgamation of artificial intelligence and analytics not only converts data into a valuable strategic tool but also drives enterprises towards a durable edge over their competitors, encouraging creativity and flexibility in the dynamic business environment (Bodla, 2024). Furthermore, the use of AI in marketing demonstrates the transformative impact on customer behavior analysis and client satisfaction through predictive analytics and AI-driven content personalization tactics [4]. This can be extremely helpful for startups looking to gain a competitive edge in the Nepali market. Furthermore, the reliability and accuracy of predictive analytics in business decision-making is highlighted by the role that machine learning approaches, like Artificial Neural Networks and Random Forest Models, play in creating strong prediction models for sales data (Konkathi 2024). Data quality, data visualization, and BI management are a few examples of the variables that affect the caliber of strategic decision-making (Abu-ALSondos, 2023). Though the nature of this association may vary at the decision level compared to firm-level findings, environmental dynamism moderates the relationship between rational decision-making and decision quality (Hough & White, 2003). The impact of corporate analytics on decision-making affordances is mediated by a data-driven culture, which also directly affects the comprehensiveness of strategic decisions (Cao & Duan, 2015).

Numerous researches have shown that AI-powered predictive analytics significantly improves cancer prognosis and therapy choices. Artificial intelligence algorithms have demonstrated promising results, ranging from predicting recurrence risk and treatment response in breast cancer based on histopathologic features (Moon et al., 2024) to evaluating tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TIL) densities for prognostic evaluation in colorectal and colon cancer (Sung Lim et al., 2023; Dong et al., 2023; Sung Lim et al., 2023). These AI algorithms identify high-risk groups with lower TIL density linked to higher recurrence rates and worse outcomes by analyzing whole-slide images stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Additionally, Yoon et al. (2024) report that AI-based computer-aided detection for mammography interpretation can anticipate invasive upgrading in ductal carcinoma in situ, which can help with treatment options. All things considered, AI-powered prediction analytics that use TIL densities from imaging data and histopathologic traits provide reliable and useful tools for individualized cancer care and therapy choices.

It has been demonstrated that having data analytics competency, which includes elements like data quality, analytical abilities, and tool sophistication, improves decision quality and efficiency in businesses. This highlights the significance of having high-quality data in decision-making processes (Ghasemaghei et al., 2018). Furthermore, the thoughtful use of AI principles in the workplace can result in better decision-making and data management, which will ultimately support sustainable business practices and operational effectiveness. The relationship between AI-powered predictive

analytics and strategic decision-making performance can therefore be positively moderated in Nepali startups by guaranteeing high data quality and availability. This is consistent with research on the effects of AI technologies on data management and decision-making processes in organizations (Jankovic et al., 2023). Predictive analytics driven by AI has a major impact on organizational performance and strategic decision-making, according to recent studies. Decision-making affordances offered by business analytics have a positive impact on organizational performance and the comprehensiveness of strategic decisions (Cao & Duan, 2015). The accuracy of predictive models is increased by the integration of AI and machine learning algorithms, which allows for proactive maintenance and increased reliability in satellite telecommunications infrastructure (Ochuba et al., 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) decision-making frameworks that integrate marketing and IT strategies have outperformed previous methods in terms of performance, with marketing strategy acting as a positive mediating factor between IT strategy and performance (Al-Surmi et al., 2021). These technologies boost decision accuracy in difficult strategic challenges, increase insights, and improve operational efficiency. However, investing in specialist skills, focusing on data quality, and resolving issues like data privacy and security concerns are necessary for successful deployment (Ochuba et al., 2024). In general, strategic decision-making processes are being transformed by AI and predictive analytics, which is improving organizational performance in a variety of industries. The relationship between AI-powered analytics and the effectiveness of strategic decision-making is moderated in part by corporate culture and preparation. Research indicates that decision-making affordances are positively impacted by business analytics, both directly and indirectly, through a data-driven culture, which in turn affects organizational performance (Cao & Duan, 2015). According to Upadhyay and Kumar (2020), organizational culture serves as a beneficial intermediary between internal analytical expertise and big data analytics capacity, hence enhancing corporate performance. Moreover, Bley et al. (2022) found a high positive correlation between AI capabilities, organizational performance, and organizational culture. In order to overcome the high failure rate of BI/BA adoption projects, readiness considerations play a critical intervening role in the relationship between business intelligence and analytics usage and firm success (Keramati, 2020). The aforementioned results highlight the significance of cultivating a positive company culture and guaranteeing preparedness to optimize the advantages of artificial intelligence-driven analytics in strategic decision-making and overall business efficacy. Although the nature of this link may be different at the choice level compared to firm-level findings, research indicates that environmental dynamism moderates the association between rational decision-making and performance (Hough & White, 2003). Through decision-making affordances, business analytics can improve strategic decision-making both directly and indirectly through a data-driven culture, which will increase organizational performance (Cao & Duan, 2015). Predictive analytics driven by artificial intelligence (AI) creates new possibilities to improve decision-making processes by automating intricate data analysis and producing forecasts that are more accurate and timelier (Dehankar et al., 2023). With the use of this technology, corporate strategy can be informed by greater insights into consumer behavior and industry trends. It does, however, also provide possible security vulnerabilities that need to be reduced (Dehankar et al., 2023). The introduction of AI into boardrooms is expected to have a substantial impact on strategic decision-making, possibly changing the pace and quality of decisions (Nayak & Dhanaraj, 2020).

2.1 Variables Development

Independent variable

The independent variable is AI-powered predictive analytics, which involves the use of AI technologies to analyze data and forecast future trends. This variable is measured by the startup's data analysis capabilities, the accuracy of predictions, and the integration of these analytics into the decision-making process.

Moderating variables

Four moderating variables are identified as factors that could influence the strength of the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance.

- **Data quality and availability-** The first is data quality and availability, which encompasses the accuracy, completeness, and accessibility of the data used in predictive analytics.
- **Technological infrastructure-** The second is technological infrastructure, referring to the computing power, software tools, and network connectivity that support AI implementation.
- **Organizational culture and readiness-** The third is organizational culture and readiness, which includes the startup's orientation towards innovation, its commitment to data-driven decision-making, and its preparedness to adopt AI technologies.
- **Regulatory environment-** Finally, the regulatory environment is considered, focusing on the clarity and comprehensiveness of regulations, the presence of supportive policies, and the ease of compliance with these regulations. Together, these variables form the basis for examining how AI-powered predictive analytics can enhance strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups, moderated by the quality of data, technological infrastructure, organizational culture, and the regulatory environment.

Dependent variable

The dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance, is defined by the effectiveness of decisions in achieving long-term business objectives and responding to market dynamics. This variable includes dimensions such as decision accuracy, decision timeliness, and the impact on business outcomes like revenue growth and market expansion.

2.2 Hypothesis development

H1: AI-powered predictive analytics significantly enhances strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

Hypothesis H1 suggests that the use of AI-powered predictive analytics by Nepali startups significantly improves their strategic decision-making performance. This means that when startups utilize AI-driven tools to analyze data and forecast trends, they are likely to make more accurate, timely, and effective strategic decisions, leading to better business outcomes such as increased revenue, market share, and customer satisfaction. The hypothesis implies that predictive analytics provides startups with critical insights that enhance their ability to navigate challenges and capitalize on opportunities, ultimately driving their growth and success in a competitive market.

H2: Data quality and availability positively moderate the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

Hypothesis 2 suggests that the quality and availability of data play a crucial role in strengthening the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups. In other words, when startups have access to high-quality and readily available data, the effectiveness of AI-powered predictive analytics in enhancing strategic decision-making is significantly amplified. Good data quality ensures that the insights generated by predictive analytics are accurate and reliable, while data availability ensures that sufficient and relevant data is accessible for analysis. Therefore, this hypothesis posits that the positive impact of predictive analytics on decision-making performance is greater when startups operate with high-quality and abundant data, enabling them to make more informed and effective strategic decisions.

H3: Technological infrastructure positively moderates the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

Hypothesis H3 posits that the strength of the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups is significantly enhanced by the quality of their technological infrastructure. This means that when startups have robust technological infrastructure such as advanced computing systems, reliable internet connectivity, and access to cutting-edge software tools their ability to effectively utilize AI-powered predictive analytics is greatly improved. As a result, these startups are better equipped to make accurate, timely, and impactful strategic decisions. In essence, the hypothesis suggests that a strong technological foundation amplifies the benefits of predictive analytics, leading to superior decision-making performance in startups.

H4: Organizational culture and readiness positively moderate the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

Hypothesis H4 proposes that the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups is positively influenced by the organization's culture and readiness for adopting new technologies. Specifically, when a startup fosters a culture that embraces innovation, data-driven decision-making, and continuous learning, and when it is prepared to integrate AI technologies into its operations, the effectiveness of AI-powered predictive analytics in improving strategic decisions is significantly enhanced. This means that startups with a supportive organizational culture and high readiness are better positioned to leverage predictive analytics tools, leading to more accurate, timely, and successful strategic decisions.

H5: The regulatory environment positively moderates the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

Hypothesis H5 suggests that the regulatory environment in which Nepali startups operate positively influences the effectiveness of AI-powered predictive analytics in enhancing strategic decision-making performance. This means that when the regulatory framework is supportive providing clear guidelines, data protection policies, and incentives for adopting new technologies the relationship between predictive analytics and decision-making performance is strengthened. In such an environment, startups are more likely to use AI-driven tools effectively, leading to better strategic decisions. Conversely, if the regulatory environment is restrictive or unclear, it may hinder the successful implementation of predictive analytics, reducing its impact on decision-making performance.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

3. Research methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study uses a quantitative research approach to investigate the impact of AI-powered predictive analytics on strategic decision-making in Nepalese companies. The quantitative approach allows for the systematic analysis of relationships between variables, resulting in a more objective and generalizable understanding of the topic under research. The study is descriptive and correlational in nature, with the goal of describing the existing practices of Nepalese entrepreneurs in terms of predictive analytics use and determining any meaningful correlations between the use of these tools and the firms' strategic outcomes.

3.2 Data collection

Data Collection Survey Instrument: A structured survey created especially for this study was used to gather data. Google form were used to get the responses. The questionnaire was broken up into sections that focused on several facets of strategic decision-making and predictive analytics. Among these sections were:

Demographic Information: To compile information on the occupations of the respondents, the size of the company, the years of operation, and the industry sector of their startups.

Use of Predictive Analytics: The questions centered on the kinds of analytics (e.g., market trend analysis, consumer behavior prediction) and how frequently startups employ AI-powered predictive analytics tools.

Strategic Decision-Making: The accuracy of market forecasts, customer acquisition tactics, product development, and overall business performance were all measured in this part to determine how effective decision-making procedures were.

Perceived Impact: Respondents were asked to use a Likert scale, with 1 denoting strongly disagree and 5 denoting strongly agree, to score the perceived impact of predictive analytics on a range of strategic outcomes.

Data Collection Process: To reach a varied sample of Nepali startups, links to the survey were disseminated through professional networks and startup incubators. The survey was distributed by email and online survey platforms. Furthermore, in order to guarantee greater participation, in-person surveys were carried out during networking sessions and startup events. For a duration of four weeks, the survey was available, giving participants the opportunity to furnish well-considered and precise answers.

3.3 Sampling and sample size

A total of 267 responds were gathered, which is above the minimum sample size required for meaningful statistical analysis. The sample size was chosen using power analysis, taking into account the population size of Nepalese startups, the predicted effect size, and the acceptable level of confidence. The structured questionnaire survey is administered to 267 E-Commerce consumers in Nepal using social media and other channels. The sample size is computed using a 95% confidence level, 6% margin of error, and a 50% ratio to Kathmandu's population size to ensure statistical significance and representativeness of Nepal's startup community.

Sample size: 267

This means 267 or more measurements/surveys are needed to have a confidence level of 95% that the real value is within $\pm 6\%$ of the measured/surveyed value.

Confidence Level: 95%
 Margin of Error: 6 %
 Population Proportion: 50 % Use 50% if not sure
 Population Size: 1442000 Leave blank if unlimited population size.

Calculate Clear

Figure 2 Sample size

4. Data analysis

The acquired data was analyzed with SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software. SPSS was chosen for its strong statistical capabilities, convenience of use, and ability to handle big datasets, making it perfect for conducting descriptive and inferential analyses in this work. The data was first subjected to descriptive analysis to offer a summary of the sample characteristics as well as the extent to which predictive analytics were adopted by the surveyed startups. Mean, median, mode, standard deviation, and frequency distributions were calculated to provide a summary of the data. Inferential statistics were used to test the research hypotheses. A correlation analysis was performed to investigate the correlations between the use of predictive analytics and strategic decision-making outcomes. Multiple regression analysis was performed to determine the predictive capacity of AI-driven data on decision-making efficacy, while accounting for other important aspects such as firm size, industry, and operational experience.

4.1 Overviews of data

A standardized Likert scale questionnaire disseminated via Google Forms was used to gather data for this investigation. In order to gather information on respondents' opinions and experiences using AI-powered predictive analytics in strategic decision-making within Nepali startups, a Likert scale was developed. The picture below provides a concise summary of the data.

4.2 Demographic data of respondents

Figure 3 Respondent's job title

With 40% of the sample, the graphic indicates that marketing managers made up the largest group of participants. This shows that the data adequately reflected the viewpoints and experiences of marketing managers. In addition, the figure shows a notable presence of data analysts (23.8%), founder-CEOs (15.5%), and technology officers (17%), offering a

cross-section of roles and areas of competence within the firms. The survey sample is further diversified by include staff members (3.4%) and counselors (0.4%), which guarantees a thorough understanding of the subject from a variety of stakeholder groups. The survey data's varied representation can improve the validity and breadth of the insights your research yields.

Figure 4 Size of the startup

The distribution of Nepali startups surveyed according to their size, classified by the number of employees, is probably depicted in the pie chart. With 44.6% of the pie, startups with 51–100 employees make up the largest part, suggesting that this is the most typical size among those polled. 22.8% of the second-largest chunk is made up of companies employing 101–200 people. This implies that a sizable percentage of Nepali companies are still in their infancy but are expanding. The smaller slices show startups that employ 1–10 people (7.9%), 11–50 people (17.2%), and more than 200 people (7.5%). This distribution offers insightful information on the Nepali startup scene, especially when examining how they embrace and apply AI to make strategic decisions.

Figure 5 Startup operation

The distribution of Nepali startups across different industries is seen in this pie chart. The retail industry accounts for the biggest portion of all startups, including 28.9% of those surveyed. This implies that there are a lot of companies in Nepal that are primarily focused on retail. With 25.2% of the startups in the finance sector, the industry is not far behind, suggesting a strong emphasis on technology-driven businesses. The areas of healthcare and education account for 20.7% and 12.4%, respectively. Technology accounts up 12% of the total, with the food industry appearing to have the smallest share. This distribution highlights the leading and developing industries in Nepal and provides insightful information on the ecosystem of startups in the nation.

Figure 6 Familiarity of respondents

According to this pie chart, a sizable percentage of respondents 43.8% are "very familiar" with an idea that is probably connected to AI or predictive analytics, while 23.6% are "moderately familiar," suggesting that the target audience has a promising degree of comprehension. Lower numbers of respondents said that they were "slightly familiar" (13.1%), "extremely familiar" (15.4%), and "not at all familiar," indicating a strong foundation for additional adoption of these technologies in Nepali businesses.

4.3 Reliability Test

The author used Cronbach's alpha to assess the questionnaire survey's internal consistency, or "reliability". It is most frequently used when you want to make sure the scale is reliable and have a lot of Likert items in your survey or questionnaire that produce a scale. Using a set of statements that define an attitude object, participants are asked to rate how much they agree or disagree with each statement using the Likert scale, a popular method in social science research. Typically, participants choose from a list of options, like "strongly disagree" or "strongly agree." The evaluation and summation of the replies yield a composite score that represents the participants' overall opinion of the item. Although summated scales don't always align with Likert's methods, McIver and Carmines (1981) note that they all adhere to the basic principles of Likert scaling.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	262	98.1
	Excluded ^a	5	1.9
	Total	267	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's	
Alpha	N of Items
.996	24

Table 1 Cronbach's Alpha Test

Out of 267 total submissions, 262 (98.1%) were deemed legitimate cases. This high validity rate indicates that the data collection and screening procedures were successful, and the results are likely to be representative of the target demographic (Nepali entrepreneurs). Only 5 replies (1.9%) were omitted from the analysis, indicating an extremely low

exclusion rate. This strengthens the validity and usability of the collected data. The 24-item scale has a Cronbach's Alpha rating of 0.996, indicating strong internal consistency. This signifies that the scale's components consistently measure the same underlying construct, and the data is dependable for future research.

4.4 Normality Test

To ascertain if a dataset is regularly distributed, statisticians employ procedures called normality tests. This is a crucial presumption for many statistical tests since large deviations in the data from a normal distribution might have an impact on the tests' accuracy. Even though Likert scale data may not perfectly adhere to normal distribution assumptions, normality testing is essential for this type of data, which is frequently used in surveys. In order to evaluate normalcy and account for potential skewness and kurtosis resulting from discrete replies, tests such as the Shapiro-Wilk test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, or visual inspections such histograms and Q-Q plots are used.

A Normality test via statistics

To choose the right central tendency measurements and statistical procedures, normality tests are essential in statistical analysis (Mishra et al., 2019). There are several ways to evaluate normalcy, such as numerical and visual approaches, and each has advantages and disadvantages of its own (Mishra et al., 2019). Zhang (1999) introduced the Q statistic, an omnibus test for normalcy that identifies abnormalities because of kurtosis or skewness. Other popular tests with variable power based on sample size and distribution are Shapiro-Wilk, Shapiro-Francia, Anderson-Darling, Cramer-Von-Mises, and Jarque-Bera (Khatun, 2021). Most people agree that the Shapiro-Wilk, Shapiro-Francia, and Anderson-Darling tests are the most effective (Khatun, 2021). Larger samples ($n > 30$) are frequently presumed to be normally distributed, which influences the sensitivity of normality tests (Manik et al., 2023). When deciding between parametric and nonparametric approaches for group comparisons, normality testing is crucial (Mishra et al., 2019).

	Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	267	3.5037	-.692	.149	-.165	.297
Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	267	3.4931	-.703	.149	-.200	.297
Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	267	3.5053	-.727	.149	-.137	.297
Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	267	3.5066	-.768	.149	.055	.297
Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	267	3.4841	-.714	.149	-.170	.297

Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	267	3.5047	-.779	.149	-.038	.297
Valid N (listwise)	267					

Table 2 Normality test by statistics report

The table of descriptive statistics offers a summary of the major variables examined during the investigation. With a mean of 3.5037, the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" indicates a moderate level of acceptance or implementation among the Nepali startups assessed. The factors that influence the effective utilization of AI-powered predictive analytics to varying degrees are suggested by the moderating variables, which include "Data quality and availability" (mean = 3.4931), "Technological infrastructure" (mean = 3.5053), "Organizational culture and readiness" (mean = 3.5066), and "Regulatory environment" (mean = 3.4841). A mean of 3.5047 for the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" indicates that the startups saw a somewhat good influence from predictive analytics on their strategic decision-making procedures. The distribution of responses is revealed by the skewness and kurtosis values; most variables have platykurtic distributions and somewhat negative skewness.

B Normality test via histogram visualization

Histograms are also employed as graphical representations of sample data to aid in the visualization of frequency distributions for continuous variables. A bell-shaped and symmetric histogram centered on the mean suggests that the variable has a regular distribution (Hair et al., 2019). This visual examination enhances statistical testing by providing additional insights into the distributional aspects of data, supporting researchers in determining the normality of their datasets. We performed visualization testing using histograms and examined whether they were normally distributed or not using SPSS. SPSS displays all normal findings, as shown below.

Figure 7 Normality Test via histogram visualizations

Based on these normality testing findings, both statistically and visually, our data is normally distributed. So we conducted additional investigation of other tests.

4.5 Descriptive analysis

		Statistics					
		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
N	Valid	267	267	267	267	267	267
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.5037	3.4931	3.5053	3.5066	3.4841	3.5047
Median		4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
Mode		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Std. Deviation		1.08215	1.09083	1.07423	1.07023	1.08669	1.08442
Variance		1.171	1.190	1.154	1.145	1.181	1.176
Skewness		-.692	-.703	-.727	-.768	-.714	-.779
Std. Error of Skewness		.149	.149	.149	.149	.149	.149
Kurtosis		-.165	-.200	-.137	.055	-.170	-.038
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.297	.297	.297	.297	.297	.297

Figure 8 Descriptive analysis

The statistics table gives useful information about the properties of the variables being studied. The analysis's reliability and robustness are ensured by the valid sample size of 267 for all variables and the absence of missing data. The independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" has a mean of 3.5037, indicating moderate adoption or implementation among the surveyed companies. The median and mean of 4.00 indicate that a considerable proportion of the responses fall within this range, reflecting a minor positive skew in the distribution. The moderating variables, such as "Data quality and availability," "Technological infrastructure," "Organizational culture and readiness," and "Regulatory environment," have similar moderate mean values ranging from 3.4841 to 3.5066. These numbers indicate that these elements may have varying degrees of influence on the effective use of AI-powered predictive analytics, and their implications should be carefully considered. The mean value of the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" is 3.5047, showing that predictive analytics has a moderately good impact on strategic decision-making processes across the surveyed businesses. The median and mode of 4.00 corroborate this finding. The standard deviation values, which range from 1.07023 to 1.09083, indicate a moderately compact clustering of data points around the means and a moderate level of variability in the responses. Interestingly, all variables have negative skewness values, indicating a somewhat left-skewed distribution with more responses concentrated at the upper end of the scale. The kurtosis values are heterogeneous, with some variables having platykurtic distributions (flatter than normal) and others having leptokurtic distributions (higher than usual), showing varying degrees of kurtosis among the variables. Overall, the statistics table provides a thorough summary of the central tendencies, variability, and distribution features of the variables under consideration, providing useful insights for further research and interpretation.

4.6 Correlation analysis

		Correlations					
		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	1	.962**	.946**	.953**	.935**	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	Pearson Correlation	.962**	1	.964**	.971**	.967**	.955**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	Pearson Correlation	.946**	.964**	1	.984**	.965**	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	Pearson Correlation	.953**	.971**	.984**	1	.966**	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	Pearson Correlation	.935**	.967**	.965**	.966**	1	.973**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001		<.001
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.942**	.955**	.960**	.960**	.973**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	267	267	267	267	267	267

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 9 Correlation analysis

The study's independent, moderating, and dependent variables are related to one another, as shown by the correlation table. With regard to all of the moderating variables, such as "Data quality and availability" (r = 0.962), "Technological infrastructure" (r = 0.946), "Organizational culture and readiness" (r = 0.953), and "Regulatory environment" (r = 0.935), the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" shows strong positive correlations. These correlations, which are statistically significant at the 0.01 level, imply that the presence of enabling factors like data availability, technological infrastructure, organizational readiness, and a supportive regulatory environment is positively correlated with the adoption and implementation of AI-powered predictive analytics. Furthermore, there is a strong positive correlation (r = 0.942) between the independent variable and the dependent variable, "Strategic decision-making performance," suggesting that higher adoption levels of AI-powered predictive analytics are linked to better strategic decision-making among the entities surveyed. Strong positive correlations between the moderating variables, which range from 0.960 to 0.984, further indicate their tight relationship and potential synergistic influence on the efficient application of AI-powered predictive analytics. Additionally, with correlation values ranging from 0.960 to 0.973, the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" has a high and positive association with each of the moderating variables. These correlations imply that elements like organizational preparedness, technology infrastructure, data quality, and favorable regulatory environments are critical for improving the performance of strategic decision-making, possibly by way of their impact on the successful adoption and application of AI-powered predictive analytics. The correlation table presents a comprehensive overview of the significant positive associations among the variables under investigation. This suggests that taking these elements into account jointly can help surveyed entities fully utilize AI-powered predictive analytics for strategic decision-making.

4.7 Regression analysis

Figure 10 Regression model and anova

The ANOVA table evaluates the model's statistical significance, while the Model Summary table gives a general picture of the regression model's performance. The dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance, and the independent/moderating factors have a strong positive association ($R = 0.968$) according to the Model Summary. The independent and moderating factors in the model account for 93.7% of the variance in the dependent variable, according to the R-Square value of 0.937. The model's goodness-of-fit is further supported by the Adjusted R-Square score of 0.936, which takes the number of predictors into consideration. The reasonably precise predictions of the model are indicated by the comparatively low Standard Error of the Estimate (0.27338). The regression model's overall significance is evaluated in the ANOVA table. The statistical significance of the regression model is established at the 0.01 level by the F-statistic value of 980.862 and the corresponding p-value < 0.001 . This indicates that the dependent variable (strategic decision-making performance) is significantly impacted by the independent and moderating variables taken together. The partitioning of the dependent variable's overall variance can be understood by looking at the Sum of Squares values. The variation described by the model is represented by the Regression Sum of Squares (293.226), and the variation that is not explained is represented by the Residual Sum of Squares (19.581). According to the moderating variables (organizational culture and readiness, data quality and availability, and technological infrastructure) and independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics), the overall results point to the statistical significance and strong predictive power of the regression model in explaining variations in strategic decision-making performance. The model's resilience and dependability are further supported by its strong R-Square value and low Standard Error of the Estimate.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.051	.058		.889	.375
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.166	.059	.165	2.805	.005
	Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	.242	.075	.244	3.237	.001
	Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	.365	.089	.361	4.093	<.001
	Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	.213	.100	.210	2.136	.034

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 11 Coefficients

The contributions of the independent and moderating variables to the dependent variable (strategic decision-making performance) are broken down in detail in the Coefficients table. When all predictor variables are zero, the dependent variable's baseline value is represented by the constant term (0.051). The coefficient of 0.166 ($p = 0.005$) for the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" is positive and statistically significant. This indicates that, while all other factors are held constant, a one-unit increase in the use of AI-powered predictive analytics is linked to a 0.166 rise in the performance of strategic decision-making. The variable in question exhibits a reasonably substantial positive impact on the dependent variable, as indicated by the standardized coefficient of 0.165. "Data quality and availability" has a standardized coefficient of 0.244 and a positive, statistically significant coefficient of 0.242 ($p = 0.001$) among the moderating variables. This suggests that enhanced data availability and quality have a favorable impact on the performance of strategic decision-making, maybe by facilitating the more efficient application of AI-powered predictive analytics. With a standardized coefficient of 0.361 and the greatest positive coefficient of 0.365 ($p < 0.001$), the moderating variable "Technological infrastructure" has a significant positive influence on the performance of strategic decision-making. The effective adoption and application of AI-powered predictive analytics, which improves the capacity for strategic decision-making, depend on a strong IT infrastructure. The variable "Organizational culture and readiness" that modifies the data has a standardized coefficient of 0.210 and a positive coefficient of 0.213 ($p = 0.034$). This shows that the performance of strategic decision-making can be positively impacted by an organization's culture and preparedness to adopt AI-powered predictive analytics. Overall, the Coefficients table shows how the moderating variables Data quality and availability, Organizational culture and readiness, and technological infrastructure and the independent variable AI-powered predictive analytics contribute positively and statistically significantly to the performance of strategic decision-making. According to the standardized coefficients, the biggest influence is made by technological infrastructure, which is followed by organizational culture and readiness, AI-powered predictive analytics, data availability and quality, and technological infrastructure.

5. Hypothesis testing

H1: AI-powered predictive analytics significantly enhances strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

This hypothesis is tested by taking linear regression and Pearson correlation between independent variables, AI-powered predictive analytics and dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance in Nepalese startups.

Correlations

		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	1	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001
	N	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.942**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	
	N	267	267

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 12 Correlation between dependent and independent variables

The study's correlation table depicts the association between the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" and the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". The Pearson correlation coefficient between these two variables is 0.942, indicating a significant positive link. The correlation value runs from -1 to 1, with higher values indicating a greater positive correlation and lower values indicating a stronger negative correlation. The correlation value of 0.942 indicates that as the adoption or deployment of AI-powered predictive analytics increases, so does the strategic decision-making performance of the studied companies. The correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (p-value < 0.001). This suggests that the observed correlation is highly unlikely to have happened by accident, and there is compelling evidence of a significant positive relationship between the two variables. The sample size for both variables is 267, indicating a sufficient sample size for the analysis. Overall, this correlation table demonstrates the study's finding of a substantial positive association between the use of AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance. The high correlation coefficient and statistical significance indicate that incorporating AI-powered predictive analytics into decision-making processes has the potential to improve strategic decision-making capabilities in the studied organizations.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.942 ^a	.887	.887	.36452

a. Predictors: (Constant), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	277.596	1	277.596	2089.200	<.001 ^b
	Residual	35.211	265	.133		
	Total	312.807	266			

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

The Model Summary and ANOVA tables show how well the regression model with the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" explains variations in the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". The Model Summary displays a R value of 0.942, showing a high positive correlation between the independent and

dependent variables. The R-Square score of 0.887 indicates that AI-powered predictive analytics can explain 88.7% of the variation in strategic decision-making performance. The Adjusted R-Square value of 0.887 validates the model's goodness-of-fit, while the comparatively low Standard Error of the Estimate (0.36452) suggests that the model's predictions are reasonably precise. The ANOVA table confirms the model's statistical significance, with an F-statistic value of 2089.200 and a p-value of < 0.001. This demonstrates that the independent variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics) has a considerable influence on the dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance). The Regression Sum of Squares (277.596) indicates the model's explained variance, whereas the Residual Sum of Squares (35.211) shows the unexplained variation. In conclusion, the high R-Square value, low Standard Error of the Estimate, and statistically significant ANOVA results indicate that the regression model with AI-powered predictive Analytics as the sole predictor is robust and can effectively explain a significant portion of the variance in strategic decision-making performance among the surveyed entities.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.197	.076		2.603	.010
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.944	.021	.942	45.708	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 13 Regression analysis between dependent and independent variables

The Coefficients table shows the separate contributions of the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" and the constant term to predicting the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". The constant term (0.197) indicates the dependent variable's baseline value when the independent variable is 0. The independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.944 and a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.942. According to the unstandardized coefficient, a one-unit rise in AI-powered predictive analytics adoption is connected with a 0.944 improvement in strategic decision-making performance, assuming all other variables remain constant. The standardized coefficient (Beta) value of 0.942 indicates that the independent variable has a significant positive effect on the dependent variable. Because the coefficients are normalized, their magnitudes can be compared, with larger values suggesting a greater effect. The independent variable's contribution to the model is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (t-statistic = 45.708, p-value < 0.001). This indicates that the observed link between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance is extremely unlikely to have happened by chance. Overall, the Coefficients table demonstrates a substantial positive association between the use of AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance. The high standardized coefficient and statistical significance indicate that incorporating AI-powered predictive analytics into decision-making processes can greatly improve the strategic decision-making capabilities of the studied organizations.

H2: Data quality and availability positively moderate the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

This hypothesis is tested by taking linear regression and Pearson correlation between independent variables, AI-powered predictive analytics and dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance in Nepalese startups and moderating variable data quality and availability

Correlations

		Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	Pearson Correlation	1	.962**	.955**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	.962**	1	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001
	N	267	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.955**	.942**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	
	N	267	267	267

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 14 correlation analysis between dependent independent and moderating variables

The correlation table depicts the correlations between the moderating variable "Data quality and availability", the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics", and the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". The moderating variable "Data quality and availability" has a significant positive connection with the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" ($r = 0.962, p < 0.001$). This shows that higher data quality and availability correlate with increased acceptance and deployment of AI-powered predictive analytics. Furthermore, the moderating variable "Data quality and availability" exhibits a substantial positive association with the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" ($r = 0.955, p < 0.001$). This suggests that higher levels of data quality and availability are linked to better strategic decision-making effectiveness across the surveyed organizations. The independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" shows a substantial positive association with the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" ($r = 0.942, p < 0.001$), supporting earlier findings. All of the correlations described above are statistically significant at the 0.01 level, as evidenced by p-values < 0.001 . The sample size for all variables is 267, indicating a sufficiently big sample size for the analysis. Overall, the correlation table shows a strong positive association between data quality and availability, the use of AI-powered predictive analytics, and strategic decision-making performance. These findings imply that guaranteeing good data quality and availability can aid in the effective application of AI-powered predictive analytics, hence improving strategic decision-making capacities in the examined companies.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.959 ^a	.920	.919	.30806

a. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Data quality and availability), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	287.753	2	143.876	1516.069	<.001 ^b
	Residual	25.054	264	.095		
	Total	312.807	266			

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Data quality and availability), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

The Model Summary and ANOVA tables shed light on the regression model's predictive power in explaining variations in the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" with the moderating variable "Data quality and availability" and the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics". The Model Summary reveals a R value of 0.959, showing a significant positive relationship between the predictors and the dependent variable. The R-Square value of 0.920 indicates that the moderating variable (data quality and availability) and the independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics) in the model account for 92% of the variance in strategic decision-making performance. The Adjusted R-Square value of 0.919 verifies the model's goodness-of-fit after controlling for the number of predictors. The comparatively low Standard Error of the Estimate (0.30806) suggests that the model's predictions are reasonably precise. The ANOVA table evaluates the overall significance of the regression model. The regression model is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (F-statistic = 1616.069, p-value < 0.001). This suggests that both the moderating and independent variables have a considerable impact on the dependent variable (performance in strategic decision-making). The Regression Sum of Squares (287.753) shows the variation in the dependent variable that the model can explain, whereas the Residual Sum of Squares (25.054) represents the unexplained variance. Overall, the findings indicate that the regression model with "Data quality and availability" as the moderating variable and "AI-powered predictive Analytics" as the independent variable is statistically significant and has high predictive power for explaining differences in strategic decision-making performance. The strong R-Square value, low Standard Error of the Estimate, and significant ANOVA results all contribute to the model's robustness and reliability.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.134	.064		2.081	.038
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.312	.064	.311	4.905	<.001
	Moderating variable (Data quality and availability)	.652	.063	.656	10.345	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 15 Regression analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

The Coefficients table shows the individual contributions of the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" and the moderating variable "Data quality and availability" to predicting the dependent variable "Strategic decision-

making performance". The constant term (0.134) indicates the dependent variable's baseline value when all predictors are zero. The unstandardized coefficient for the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" is 0.312, while the standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.311. When the moderating variable is held constant, the unstandardized coefficient shows that a one-unit rise in the adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics leads to a 0.312 increase in strategic decision-making performance. The unstandardized coefficient for the moderating variable "Data quality and availability" is 0.652, while the standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.656. The unstandardized coefficient indicates that a one-unit increase in data quality and availability is connected with a 0.652 increase in strategic decision-making performance when the independent variable is held constant. The standardized coefficients (Beta) make it possible to compare the predictors' respective strengths. The moderating variable "Data quality and availability" has a higher standardized coefficient (0.656) than the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" (0.311), indicating that data quality and availability have a greater positive impact on strategic decision-making performance in this model. The independent and moderating variables had t-statistic values of 4.905 and 10.345, respectively, with corresponding p-values < 0.001, showing statistically significant contributions to the model at the 0.01 level. Overall, the Coefficients table demonstrates that both the independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics) and the moderating variable (data quality and availability) have a positive and statistically significant impact on strategic decision-making performance. However, the larger standardized coefficient for data quality and availability shows that it has a greater impact on improving strategic decision-making capacities among surveyed entities when combined with the use of AI-powered predictive analytics.

H3: Technological infrastructure positively moderates the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

This hypothesis is tested by taking linear regression and Pearson correlation between independent variables, AI-powered predictive analytics and dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance in Nepalese startups and moderating variable technological infrastructure.

Correlations

		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	1	.946**	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	Pearson Correlation	.946**	1	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001
	N	267	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.942**	.960**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	
	N	267	267	267

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 16 Correlation analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

The dependent variable, "Strategic decision-making performance," the moderating variable, "Technological infrastructure," and the independent variable, "AI-powered predictive Analytics," are all strongly positively correlated, as the correlation table shows. The independent variable shows statistical significance at the 0.01 level with correlations of 0.942 with the dependent variable and 0.946 with the moderating variable. Likewise, there is a high positive

correlation ($r = 0.960$) between the moderating variable and the dependent variable. These high correlation coefficients imply that the examined entities' ability to make strategic decisions can be greatly improved by implementing AI-powered predictive analytics in conjunction with a strong technology infrastructure. The constant positive correlations found in all pairings of variables highlight how crucial it is to combine sophisticated analytical skills with sufficient technology resources in order to fully utilize their potential for enhancing strategic decision-making processes.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.965 ^a	.932	.932	.28355

a. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	291.581	2	145.790	1813.301	<.001 ^b
	Residual	21.226	264	.080		
	Total	312.807	266			

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

The moderating variable "Technological infrastructure" and the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" are used as predictors in the Model Summary and ANOVA tables to assess the regression model's predictive ability in explaining variations in the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". There is a significant positive correlation ($R = 0.965$) between the predictors and the dependent variable, according to the Model Summary. With an R-Square value of 0.932, the moderating and independent variables in the model account for 93.2% of the variance in the performance of strategic decision-making. The model's goodness-of-fit is supported by the Adjusted R-Square of 0.932, and the Standard Error of the Estimate (0.28355) indicates that the predictions were made with a reasonable degree of precision. With an F-statistic of 1813.301 and a p-value < 0.001 , the ANOVA table supports the statistical significance of the model and shows that the moderating and independent variables together have a substantial effect on the performance of strategic decision-making.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.056	.060		.928	.354
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.325	.050	.325	6.562	<.001
	Moderating variable (Technological infrastructure)	.659	.050	.653	13.189	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 17 Regression analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

The contributions of the moderating variable "technological infrastructure" and the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" to the prediction of the dependent variable "strategic decision-making performance" are shown in the Coefficients table. When both predictor variables are zero, the dependent variable's baseline value is represented by the constant term (0.056). The standardized coefficient (Beta) and unstandardized coefficient (0.325) for the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" are both 0.325. This indicates that, when the moderating variable is held constant, a one-unit rise in the use of AI-powered predictive analytics is linked to a 0.325 increase in the performance of strategic decision-making. The statistical significance of this variable's contribution is indicated by the t-statistic (6.562) and corresponding p-value < 0.001.

The standardized coefficient (Beta) for the moderating variable "Technological infrastructure" is 0.653, whereas its unstandardized coefficient is 0.659. This indicates that, when the independent variable is held constant, a one-unit increase in technological infrastructure is linked to a 0.659-unit rise in strategic decision-making performance. The statistical significance of this variable's contribution is confirmed by the t-statistic (13.189) and p-value < 0.001/2. It is clear from comparing the standardized coefficients (Beta) that in this model, "Technological infrastructure" (0.653) positively affects strategic decision-making performance slightly more than "AI-powered predictive analytics" (0.325). Overall, the Coefficients table shows how both the moderating variable technological infrastructure and the independent variable AI-powered predictive analytics contribute positively and statistically significantly to the performance of strategic decision-making. When taken into account with the adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics, the moderating variable (technological infrastructure) appears to have a little higher influence on improving strategic decision-making capacities across the surveyed entities.

H4: Organizational culture and readiness positively moderate the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

This hypothesis is tested by taking linear regression and Pearson correlation between independent variables, AI-powered predictive analytics and dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance in Nepalese startups and moderating variable organizational culture.

Correlations

		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	1	.953**	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	Pearson Correlation	.953**	1	.960**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001
	N	267	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.942**	.960**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	
	N	267	267	267

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 18 Correlation analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

Strong positive correlations are seen in the correlation table between the dependent variable, "Strategic decision-making performance," the moderating variable, "Organizational culture and readiness," and the independent variable, "AI-powered predictive Analytics." In particular, a strong positive link is shown by the independent variable's correlation coefficient of 0.942 with the dependent variable. At the 0.01 level, this association is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). There is a 0.953 connection between the moderating variable "Organizational culture and readiness" and the independent variable, and a 0.960 correlation with the dependent variable. These strong positive correlations imply that the adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics and improved strategic decision-making performance are favorably correlated with an organizational culture that is open to change and technologically prepared. Based on stated p-values less than 0.001, all associations listed are statistically significant at the 0.01 level. The significance of incorporating advanced analytics capabilities, such as AI-powered predictive analytics, into companies with a supportive culture and technology preparedness is underscored by the consistently favorable correlations observed across all variable pairs. The performance of strategic decision-making procedures as a whole can be greatly enhanced by this combination. A sizable dataset for the investigation is shown by the sample size of 267 for all variables.

In summary, the correlation table highlights the mutually reinforcing connections among the adoption of AI-driven predictive analytics, organizational culture and preparedness, and strategic decision-making effectiveness. It also highlights the necessity of adopting a comprehensive strategy to fully utilize advanced analytics in decision-making.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.964 ^a	.930	.929	.28848

a. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	290.836	2	145.418	1747.327	<.001 ^b
	Residual	21.971	264	.083		
	Total	312.807	266			

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

The regression model incorporating the moderating variable "organizational culture and readiness" and the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" is assessed in the Model Summary and ANOVA tables for its ability to predict the dependent variable "strategic decision-making performance". There is a high positive correlation ($R = 0.964$) between the predictors and the dependent variable, according to the Model Summary. The moderating and independent variables in the model account for 93% of the variance in strategic decision-making performance, according to the R-Square value of 0.930. The model's goodness-of-fit is confirmed by the Adjusted R-Square of 0.929, which takes the number of predictors into consideration. The reasonably precise predictions made by the model are indicated by the comparatively low Standard Error of the Estimate (0.28848). The regression model's overall significance is evaluated in the ANOVA table. According to the p -value < 0.001 and the F-statistic value of 1747.327, the regression model is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This indicates that the dependent variable (strategic decision-making performance) is significantly impacted by both the independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics) and the moderating variable (organizational culture and preparation).

The variation in the dependent variable that the model is able to explain is represented by the Regression Sum of Squares (290.836), whilst the unexplained variation is represented by the Residual Sum of Squares (21.971). To sum up, the regression model's robustness and reliability in predicting the performance of strategic decision-making using organizational culture and readiness as the moderating variable and AI-powered predictive analytics as the independent variable are reinforced by the high R-Square value, low Standard Error of the Estimate, and statistically significant ANOVA results.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.056	.061		.923	.357
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.298	.054	.297	5.537	<.001
	Moderating variable (Organizational culture and readiness)	.686	.054	.677	12.613	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 19 Regression analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

The Coefficients table reveals the specific contributions of the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" and the moderating variable "Organizational culture and readiness" to predicting the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance". The constant term (0.056) denotes the dependent variable's baseline value when both predictor variables are 0.

The unstandardized coefficient for the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" is 0.298, while the standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.297. This suggests that a one-unit rise in AI-powered predictive analytics adoption is connected with a 0.298 improvement in strategic decision-making performance, assuming the moderating variable remains constant. This variable's impact is statistically significant, as indicated by the t-statistic (5.537) and p-value (< 0.001). The unstandardized coefficient for the moderating variable "Organizational culture and readiness" is 0.686, whereas the standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.677. This implies that a one-unit rise in organizational culture and readiness is connected with a 0.686 increase in strategic decision-making performance, assuming the independent variable remains constant. The t-statistic (12.613) and p-value < 0.001 indicate the statistical importance of this variable's contribution. When the standardized coefficients (Beta) are compared, it is clear that "organizational culture and readiness" (0.677) has a greater positive impact on strategic decision-making performance in this model than "AI-

powered predictive analytics" (0.297). Overall, the Coefficients table demonstrates that both the independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics) and the moderating variable (organizational culture and preparation) provide positive and statistically significant contributions to strategic decision-making success. However, when combined with the deployment of AI-powered predictive analytics, the moderating variable (organisational culture and readiness) appears to have a greater influence on improving strategic decision-making capacities among the studied organizations.

H5: The regulatory environment positively moderates the relationship between AI-powered predictive analytics and strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

This hypothesis is tested by taking linear regression and Pearson correlation between independent variables, AI-powered predictive analytics and dependent variable, strategic decision-making performance in Nepalese startups and moderating variable regulatory environment.

Correlations

		Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)
Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	Pearson Correlation	1	.935**	.942**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001
	N	267	267	267
Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	Pearson Correlation	.935**	1	.973**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001
	N	267	267	267
Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)	Pearson Correlation	.942**	.973**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	
	N	267	267	267

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 20 Correlation analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

Strong positive correlations are shown in the correlation table between the dependent variable, "Strategic decision-making performance," the moderating variable, "Regulatory environment," and the independent variable, "AI-powered predictive Analytics. "The adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics and the performance of strategic decision-making are strongly positively correlated, as shown by the independent variable's correlation coefficient of 0.942 with the dependent variable. At the 0.01 level, this association is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

There is a 0.935 connection between the moderating variable "Regulatory environment" and the independent variable, and a 0.973 correlation with the dependent variable. These strong positive correlations imply that the use of AI-powered predictive analytics and improved strategic decision-making performance are positively correlated with a supportive regulatory environment.

Based on stated p-values less than 0.001, all associations listed are statistically significant at the 0.01 level. The significance of incorporating advanced analytics capabilities, such as AI-powered predictive analytics, in firms functioning within regulatory frameworks that are favorable is underscored by the consistently positive correlations observed across all variable pairs. The performance of strategic decision-making procedures as a whole can be greatly enhanced by this combination. A sizable dataset for the investigation is shown by the sample size of 267 for all variables. Overall, the correlation table highlights the positive relationships that exist between the adoption of AI-powered predictive analytics, a supportive regulatory environment, and the ability to make strategic decisions. This highlights the necessity of having a supportive regulatory environment in order to fully utilize advanced analytics in decision-making.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.978 ^a	.956	.955	.22905

a. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Regulatory environment), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	298.956	2	149.478	2849.171	<.001 ^b
	Residual	13.850	264	.052		
	Total	312.807	266			

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Moderating variable (Regulatory environment), Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)

The regression model that uses the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" and the moderating variable "Regulatory environment" to predict the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" is explained by the Model Summary and ANOVA tables. With a R value of 0.978, the Model Summary demonstrates a very high positive correlation between the predictors and the dependent variable. The moderating and independent variables in the model account for 95.6% of the variance in strategic decision-making performance, according to the R-Square value of 0.956. After adjusting for the number of predictors, the model's exceptional goodness-of-fit is confirmed by the Adjusted R-Square of 0.955. The model predicts with a high degree of precision, as evidenced by the comparatively low Standard Error of the Estimate (0.22905). The regression model's overall significance is evaluated in the ANOVA table. The statistical significance of the regression model is demonstrated at the 0.01 level by the F-statistic value of 2849.171 and the corresponding p-value < 0.001. This indicates that the dependent variable (strategic decision-making performance) is significantly impacted by the independent variable (AI-powered predictive analytics) and the moderating variable (Regulatory environment). The residual sum of squares (13.850) shows the comparatively minor unexplained variance, whereas the regression sum of squares (298.956) shows the significant variation in the dependent variable explained by the model. In conclusion, the regression model's remarkable robustness and reliability in predicting strategic decision-making performance using the regulatory environment as the moderating variable and AI-powered predictive analytics as the independent variable are reinforced by the very high R-Square value, low Standard Error of the Estimate, and statistically significant ANOVA results.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.054	.048		1.125	.262
	Independent Variable (AI-powered predictive Analytics)	.254	.037	.253	6.944	<.001
	Moderating variable (Regulatory environment)	.735	.036	.736	20.178	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Dependent variable (Strategic decision-making performance)

Figure 21 Regression analysis between dependent, independent and moderating variables

The contributions of the moderating variable "Regulatory environment" and the independent variable "AI-powered predictive analytics" to the prediction of the dependent variable "Strategic decision-making performance" are delineated in the Coefficients table. When both predictor variables are zero, the dependent variable's baseline value is represented by the constant term (0.054). The standardized coefficient (Beta) for the independent variable "AI-powered predictive Analytics" is 0.253, whereas the unstandardized coefficient is 0.254. This indicates that, when the moderating variable is held constant, a one-unit rise in the use of AI-powered predictive analytics is linked to a 0.254 increase in the performance of strategic decision-making. The statistical significance of this variable's contribution is indicated by the t-statistic (6.944) and associated p-value < 0.001. "Regulatory environment" is the moderating variable. Its standardized coefficient (Beta) is 0.736, whereas its unstandardized coefficient is 0.735. This indicates that, when the independent variable is held constant, a one-unit rise in a supportive regulatory environment is linked to a 0.735 increase in strategic decision-making performance. The statistical significance of this variable's contribution is confirmed by the t-statistic (20.178) and p-value < 0.001. It is clear from comparing the standardized coefficients (Beta) that in this model, "Regulatory environment" (0.736) has a greater positive influence on the performance of strategic decision-making than "AI-powered predictive Analytics" (0.253). Overall, the Coefficients table shows how both the moderating variable the regulatory environment and the independent variable AI-powered predictive analytics contribute positively and statistically significantly to the performance of strategic decision-making. When taken into account in conjunction with the use of AI-powered predictive analytics, the moderating variable (Regulatory environment) seems to have a greater impact on improving strategic decision-making capacities among the surveyed businesses.

6. Result and discussion

This study's findings, which included a survey of 267 Nepali startups, included a number of noteworthy discoveries. First, there were significant positive correlations found between the performance of strategic decision-making, the moderating variables (organizational culture and preparation, technological infrastructure, and regulatory environment), and the use of AI-powered predictive analytics. The statistical significance of these connections indicates that these elements interact to improve decision-making abilities in Nepali entrepreneurs. Additionally, the regression models showed a very good fit, with high R-square values ranging from 0.930 to 0.956. This means that a significant amount of the variance in the performance of strategic decision-making was well described by the moderating variables and AI-powered predictive analytics. The overall statistical significance of these regression models was further supported by the ANOVA results. Examining the coefficients analysis in more detail reveals that the moderating variables and the use of AI-powered predictive analytics both had positive and statistically significant effects on the performance of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups. The regulatory environment was found to have the biggest beneficial influence on the performance of strategic decision-making among the moderating variables. This was followed by organizational culture and preparation, and technology infrastructure.

These results highlight how important AI-powered predictive analytics are to improving the performance of strategic decision-making in Nepali startups. However, a number of organizational and environmental elements unique to the startup ecosystem in Nepal mitigate the impact of this enhanced analytical skill. First and foremost, Nepali startups must have a strong technology foundation in place to enable the efficient application and use of AI-powered predictive analytics. Startups may more effectively use these analytics tools and convert findings into better strategic decision-making if they have a solid technological base.

Second, it's critical to have an organizational culture that is open to change and prepared for technology. These new and dynamic businesses can benefit from the effective adoption and integration of AI-powered predictive analytics by

fostering a culture that values innovation, continuous learning, and data-driven decision-making processes. This will strengthen their capacity for strategic decision-making.

Thirdly, one important moderating factor that emerged was Nepal's regulatory environment. Startups in Nepal can benefit from adopting and using AI-powered predictive analytics if the regulatory environment is supportive and encouraging. This will allow them to make better use of these sophisticated analytical tools when making strategic decisions. On the other hand, the adoption and application of these technologies may be impeded by a restrictive or unclear regulatory framework, which could limit their influence on the performance of strategic decision-making within the Nepali startup ecosystem.

Overall, this study highlights how organizational characteristics, technology developments, and external environmental factors all interact to shape how successful AI-powered predictive analytics is for strategic decision-making in Nepali startups. Adopting these cutting-edge analytical methods is clearly advantageous, but in the Nepali context, their effects are enhanced by a strong technology foundation, a supportive corporate culture, and a favorable regulatory framework. To fully realize the promise of AI-powered predictive analytics, Nepali entrepreneurs looking to improve their strategic decision-making abilities should take a comprehensive approach that takes into account these interconnected aspects.

7. Limitations and future research

It is important to recognize several limitations and possible areas for future research, even if this study offers insightful information about the function of AI-powered predictive analytics and the moderating factors influencing strategic decision-making performance in Nepali startups.

First, survey data from a sample of 267 Nepali startups was used in the study. Despite being a reasonably big sample size, it could not be completely representative of Nepal's diversified and quickly changing startup environment. Subsequent studies may seek to increase the sample size and guarantee a more thorough portrayal of startups in different industries, phases of development, and regions of Nepal. Second, four important moderating variables were the focus of the investigation. Nevertheless, there might be more moderating variables that affect how well AI-powered predictive analytics work for making strategic decisions. To acquire a more comprehensive comprehension of the relationship between these characteristics and the implementation of sophisticated analytics in Nepali startups, future research endeavors may investigate supplementary moderating variables. Thirdly, although the study looked at how AI-powered predictive analytics affected the performance of strategic decision-making, it didn't go into detail on the particular kinds of strategic decisions or the decision-making procedures used by Nepali entrepreneurs. Subsequent studies may examine the ways in which AI-driven predictive analytics impacts several facets of strategic decision-making, including but not limited to market entry tactics, product development, resource distribution, and risk mitigation. Furthermore, qualitative research techniques like case studies or in-depth interviews could support the study's quantitative results. Deeper insights into the experiences, difficulties, and best practices related to implementing AI-powered predictive analytics in Nepali startups, as well as the organizational dynamics and decision-making processes involved, may be obtained through the use of such qualitative methodologies. Furthermore, future studies should examine the effects of cutting-edge technologies like machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing on strategic decision-making in Nepali startups, given how quickly the fields of artificial intelligence and predictive analytics are developing. Comprehending the possible consequences of these innovative technologies could aid startups in staying ahead of the curve and preserving a competitive advantage in the ever-changing business environment.

Finally, longitudinal research might be done to find out how AI-powered predictive analytics affects Nepali startups' performance and growth paths over the long run. The results of these research may be useful in influencing the creation of supporting policies and efforts within the Nepali startup ecosystem as well as educating strategic decision-making regarding the long-term effects of these cutting-edge analytical tools and the moderating factors that change over time. Researchers and practitioners can gain a deeper understanding of the role AI-powered predictive analytics plays in strategic decision-making by addressing these limitations and investigating the recommended areas for future research. They can also help Nepali startups thrive in an increasingly data-driven and technologically enabled business environment.

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